

Figure 4A



Figure 4A



Figure 4A



Figure 4A



Figure 4A



Figure 4A





Figure 4B IP Fyn



Figure 4B

IP Tim-3



Figure 4B IP p-STAT3



Figure 4B WCL Fyn



Figure 4B WCL Tim-3



Figure 4B WCL p-STAT3



Figure 4B WCL STAT3



Figure 4B

WCL GAPDH



Figure 4C



Figure 4C



Figure 4C



Figure 4C



Figure 4C



Figure 4C





Figure 7C



Figure 7C

